

PERCEPTION OF QUALITY OF LIFE OF ELEMENTARY EDUCATION TEACHERS

PERCEPCIÓN DE LA CALIDAD DE VIDA DE LOS DOCENTES DE EDUCACIÓN PRIMARIA

PERCEPÇÃO DA QUALIDADE DE VIDA DE DOCENTES DO ENSINO FUNDAMENTAL

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Abstract

This work falls within the field of studies related to the quality of life of education workers, specifically referring to elementary school teachers. It aimed to analyze the perception of quality of life among elementary school teachers. This research included teachers from the municipal school system of a municipality in southwestern Bahia. We used a questionnaire validated by Moreira, Mussi, and Cardoso (2022) to obtain sociodemographic data. Regarding quality of life, we used the WHOQOL-Bref questionnaire, drawing on the philosophical currents of Historical and Dialectical Materialism. We adopted both a quantitative and qualitative methodological approach. The data were exported from Google Forms to an Excel spreadsheet and subsequently analyzed using SPSS version 20.0 software, using inferential statistics, analyzing the absolute frequency of the results. The results indicated a significant association between biological sex and quality of life ($p=0.046$), highlighting greater vulnerability among women, especially in the physical and psychological domains. It was found that working conditions and gender inequalities directly impact teacher well-being and retention. The study contributes to the debate on health, recognition, and public policies aimed at improving the working conditions of basic education teachers.

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Resumen

Este trabajo se enmarca en el campo de los estudios relacionados con la calidad de vida de los trabajadores de la educación, específicamente en lo que respecta al profesorado de primaria. Su objetivo fue analizar la percepción de la calidad de vida del profesorado de primaria. Esta investigación incluyó a docentes del sistema escolar municipal de un municipio del suroeste de Bahía. Se utilizó un cuestionario validado por Moreira, Mussi y Cardoso (2022) para obtener datos sociodemográficos. En cuanto a la calidad de vida, se utilizó el cuestionario WHOQOL-Bref, basado en las corrientes filosóficas del Materialismo Histórico y Dialéctico. Se adoptó un enfoque metodológico tanto cuantitativo como cualitativo. Los datos se exportaron de Formularios de Google a una hoja de cálculo de Excel y posteriormente se analizaron con el software SPSS versión 20.0, mediante estadística inferencial, analizando la frecuencia absoluta de los resultados. Los resultados indicaron una asociación significativa entre el sexo biológico y la calidad de vida ($p = 0,046$), destacando una mayor vulnerabilidad entre las mujeres, especialmente en los dominios físico y psicológico. Se encontró que las condiciones laborales y las desigualdades de género inciden directamente en el bienestar y la retención docente. El estudio contribuye al debate sobre la salud, el reconocimiento y las políticas públicas orientadas a mejorar las condiciones de trabajo del profesorado de educación básica.

Palabras clave: Educación primaria; Calidad de vida; Maestros.

Resumo

Este trabalho enquadra-se no campo de estudos relacionados à qualidade de vida dos trabalhadores da educação. Refere-se, mais especificamente, ao docente do Ensino Fundamental. Teve como objetivo analisar a percepção de qualidade de vida do docente do ensino fundamental. Fizeram parte desta pesquisa professores da Rede Municipal de um município no sudoeste da Bahia. Como instrumentos utilizamos um questionário validado por Moreira, Mussi e Cardoso (2022), visando obter os dados sociodemográficos, sobre qualidade de vida utilizamos o questionário WHOQOL-Bref, recorremos a corrente filosófica do Materialismo Histórico e Dialético. Trouxe a abordagem metodológica quantitativa e qualitativa. Os dados foram exportados do Google Forms para uma planilha do Excel e, posteriormente, analisados pelo software SPSS versão 20.0, utilizando a estatística inferencial, analisando a frequência absoluta dos resultados. Os resultados indicaram associação significativa entre sexo biológico e qualidade de vida ($p=0,046$), evidenciando maior vulnerabilidade entre mulheres, especialmente nos domínios físico e psicológico. Constatou-se que as condições de trabalho e as desigualdades de gênero interferem diretamente no bem-estar e na permanência docente. O estudo contribui para o debate sobre saúde, valorização e políticas públicas voltadas à melhoria das condições de trabalho dos professores da educação básica.

Palavras-chave: Docentes; Ensino Fundamental; Qualidade de vida.

Introduction

This work field is about the quality of life of elementary teachers in Brazil. We focus on the experience of these professionals in their work and its challenges, such as: crowded classrooms, poor structure in schools, desvalorization¹, illness, tiredness, low

salaries, low recognition, among others. Those factors may affect this professional category with some psychological and emotional risks, among others.

There are several changes in the teaching field. In the last decades, there was a lot of ampliation of the social issues getting through school. It also impacts on the amount of work that the teacher has to finish. It fragilizes the material and symbolical conditions of the work. Although it may seem widely defended in public policies and educational discourses, the teacher valorization isn't yet applied in a consistent way in the forms of improvements at the careers, at the salaries and in the work conditions. All this directly impacts in the well-being and in the quality of life of these professionals (Gatti, 2020; Campos, Vérias; Araújo, 2020).

Teachers face long work hours, insufficient planning, and unequal pay as their careers progress. This issue contributes significantly to the desvalorization of the field. All this causes psychological and physical problems (Pascoal; Silva, 2019). The lack of wealth interferes with the quality of life.

These issues are much more visible at public schools in the small cities. These cities have many more problems due to their lack of resources, to the multiplicity of functions that teachers have to do and the absence of effective institutional support. Studies conducted by Oswaldo Cruz Foundation (Fiocruz, 2022), Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OCDE, 2023) and National Institute of Educational Studies and Research Anísio Teixeira (INEP, 2021) shows that the physical and emotional suffering of teachers are related both to the intensity of pedagogical work and to the social desvalorization of teacher work. It has a direct impact on mental health and at the continuity of the work.

The focus on elementary teachers stems from their crucial role in educating children and adolescents. Elementary education, encompassing both the early and later years, not only introduces students to the world of knowledge but also develops fundamental social – emotional, cognitive and ethical skills essential for their life in society. In this context, the teacher takes on an essential and complex role, becoming a transformative agent in the teaching – learning process.

The discussion about the quality of life of elementary school teachers is extremely relevant, especially considering the challenges faced by these professionals in recent decades. The state of the art produced by Azevêdo and Cardoso (2024) highlighted the scarcity of studies addressing the topic of quality of life among elementary school teachers. The search was carried out in the Thesis and Dissertation Database of the Coordination for the Improvement of Higher Education Personnel (CAPES), the Digital Library of Theses and Dissertations (BDTD), and the Graduate Program in Education (PPGED) at UESB.

Another significant consideration is the potential impact of limited research on educational public policy. In the absence of comprehensive data and studies, policymakers may encounter challenges when designing effective strategies to enhance teacher's working conditions. This situation could contribute to perpetuating low morale among educators, which in turn can have direct implications for students' outcomes.

The central concept in this study is quality of life. It is understood in a wide and multidimensional form. It englobes physical, psychological, social and ambiantal factors. Those factors influence the individuals in the way that the individual perceives existence and the own role in world (World Health Organization - OMS, 1998). In the educational context, this concept shows as an important indicator for the analysis of real work conditions, the engagement and the professional motivation. It is also connected to the quality of the educational process offered to students (Oliveira; Santos; Dias, 2017; OCDE, 2022).

In this work, the concept of quality of life is understood according to the OMS (1998) but reinterpreted in light of the material and symbolic conditions of teaching. It is therefore different from subjective well-being – which involves an individual's perception of satisfaction – and from physical or mental health – which are more closely linked to the objective conditions of work.

National and international research reinforces that teacher well-being is not limited to the absence of illness, but also involves symbolic recognition, pedagogical autonomy, and interpersonal relationships built within the school environment (Fiocruz, 2022; UNESCO, 2023). Understanding these factors is essential to guide policies for teacher appreciation and ongoing professional development, which can promote not only the individual health of teacher but also the sustainability of educational practices.

The aim of this study is to analyze the perception of quality of life among elementary school teachers in the public school system of a municipality in the southwest of Bahia, seeking to identify both sociodemographic and work-related factors that influence this perception and to assess how the physical, psychological, social, and environmental domain relate to working conditions and to the meaning attributed to teaching.

Therefore, by bringing together quantitative indicators and qualitative interpretations, this study aims to contribute to the discussion on health, teacher appreciation, and public policies focused on the teaching profession, providing support for the development of strategies that promote dignity, recognition, and well-being in the daily life of schools.

- What is quality of life?

The term Quality of Life (QoL) is not new, since discussions about quality of life have existed since 1920. At that time, According to Kluthcovsky and Takayanagui, “by Arthur Cecil Pigou, a British economist, in a book dealing with economics and material well-being”, although the term was not valued at the time (Kluthcovsky; Takayanagui, 2007, p. 14). According to Ruidiaz-Gómez and Cacante-Caballero (2021), the concern with scientifically evaluating the concept arose around the 1960s, amid social changes and new epidemiological models related to health disease.

In this context, global cultural, political and economic transformations influenced the way health and well-being were perceived. The emergence of new epidemiological models led to a broader view of health, which came to include not only the absence of disease but also mental, physical and social well-being.

Pereira et al. (2012) emphasized that there are records showing that United States President Lyndon Johnson used the term in a speech at the University of Michigan in 1964, in which he spoke about people’s interest in a “good life” or “quality life”. However, to this day, further studies are needed to fully understand the meaning of the term quality of life.

The expression “quality of life” is broad and encompasses various factors related to health such as physical, functional, emotional, and mental well-being, as well as those not directly related to health, including work, family, friends, and other aspects of life. Considering quality of life prompts an examination of its definition. There is a great variety of definitions for this concept.

According to the World Health Organization (WHO, 1998), quality of life refers to how people perceive whether their needs are being met or whether they are being denied opportunities to achieve happiness and self-fulfillment, regardless of their physical health or the social and economic conditions in which they live.

The concept of quality of life presented by WHO highlights an essential aspect: it is not limited to objective factors such as physical health conditions, income, or access to material resources, but decisively involves the subjective perception everyone has of their own existence. The WHO’s concept of quality of life includes not only objective factors like health and income, but also each person’s subjective assessment of their own life.

In other words, quality of life is shaped by how a person interprets and assigns meaning to their experiences, values and expectations. Thus, elements such as happiness, a sense of personal fulfillment, and emotional well-being become central to understanding quality of life. These items highlight how external factors and individual experience interact.

The idea that the needs should be taken care of is central. People feel more plenitude and contentment with their lives when their emotional, social and psychological needs are fulfilled. Moreover, the emphasis on independence from health status suggests that even in challenging circumstances, such as illness or financial difficulties, people can still find ways to experience happiness and personal fulfillment.

Minayo, Hartz and Buss (2000) states that quality of life is a human notion. It has been approximated to the degree of contentment found in family, romantic, social and environmental life, as well as with the very aesthetics of existence. Based on the discussion by the authors, it can be inferred that quality of life is something unique and essentially human, deeply connected to the experiences people have in different aspects of their lives. In this context, by addressing the satisfaction found in family, romantic, social, and environmental life, they encompass various areas where quality of life can be experienced, including at work.

According to Moretti (2007), quality of work life (QWL) involves factors such as people, occupations, and organizations, with particular emphasis on concern for employee well-being and organizational effectiveness, as well as employee participation in decisions related to work.

Therefore, when considering quality of life in the professional environment, ensuring proper working conditions, recognition, and emotional support not only benefits individual performance but also fosters a more harmonious and productive atmosphere. Cardoso Junior, Cardoso and Nunes (2025, p. 36) affirm that “In addition to physical and psychological health, independence, social relationships, and personal beliefs, the broader interactions individuals have with their environments would be determining factors”. In this way, reflecting on quality of life invites us to take a holistic view of the human being, valuing every aspect of existence and recognizing that true well-being goes beyond material conditions, also encompassing the emotional and social dimensions that connect us to one another.

Methodology

Conducting scientific Research requires the researcher to have a coherent epistemological basis. The researcher should know a detailed study of the reasons, premises, and hypotheses that led them to pursue a particular topic. Research can be defined as organized information constructed around a set of concepts that can be examined and validated from a scientific perspective so that they become part of scientific knowledge.

This article uses the documentary research, employing a quantitative – qualitative approach, grounded in the framework of Historical-Dialectical Materialism. The study was conducted within the public elementary education system in a municipality in southwestern Bahia, with the Municipal Department of Education and the municipal schools serving as the research sites.

Gatti (2010, p. 9-10) asserted that: “research is the act through which we seek to gain knowledge about something. [...] However, in a stricter sense, it aims at creating a body of knowledge on a certain subject”. In this way, we support Gatti’s ideas by stating that the practice of research has attributes.

Pires (1997) highlighted that working on education, whether as a teacher or researcher, places us in a position that requires us to understand the many different elements involved in educational practice, demanding that we comprehend education and teaching as fully as possible. From this perspective, for this to occur, we need a method that can guide our understanding of education.

This study presents the philosophical current of Historical -Dialectical Materialism (HMD) as an inspiration for interpreting social reality. According to Cardoso Junior, Nunes, and Cardoso (2022, p. 182), “The Materialism that articulates Marx’s method of analysis is the indication for a way of looking at the reality to be studied, one that does not dispense with prior ideation or previous thought about the reality”. Thus, it begins with the necessity to study and understand reality to achieve success in the search.

We understand that, for Marx (2013), philosophical thinking does not consist of a set of precepts to follow. Instead, it is the result of the researcher’s relationship with the object, involving an understanding of its determinations. For this reason, it is important to emphasize that the relationship between the subject and the object of study is essential in this research process. Martins and Lavoura (2018) highlight the importance of the object for research.

It is necessary to extract from the object its determinations, as they are constitutive of it and can Only be reached and reproduced in thought through the investigator’s process of analytical abstraction, which relies on analytical categories and the concepts embodied within them. (Martins; Lavoura, 2018, p. 228)

According to the Materialism Historical – Dialectical (HDM), it is necessary to understand reality considering the relations and determinations that forms the object of analysis, showing the connection between the subject and the object. This philosophical thinking allows to address a contradiction present in Brazilian education, when women make up most of the teaching profession.

According to Marxist thinking, this reality cannot be analyzed isolated or out of context. On the contrary, it should be understood in its historical, social and economic determinations that shapes the educational field. The predominant presence of women in teaching, for example, can be seen because of historical process that stablished a sexual division of word, giving to women functions related to the homework and

education, frequently social and economic unvaluable, situation that can reflect in the reduction of quality of life.

As for the methodological approach, this text uses both quantitative and qualitative methods, considering that both are widely employed, utilizing questionnaires and interviews with the subjects themselves that yield comparable results.

According to Minayo (2001, p. 21), “qualitative research works with the universe of meanings, motives, beliefs, values, and attitudes, corresponding to a deeper space of relationships, processes, and phenomena”. According to Bogdan and Biklen (1994) the qualitative approach requires that the world be investigated with the idea that nothing is trivial. From this perspective, the choice of the qualitative approach arises from the desire to interpret the problem based on what is learned in the researched environment, since it is important to experience and focus on the process, not just the result.

Quantitative research can be defined as a method that produces numerical data on objective issues in a standardized format. This type of research is widely used due to the practicality of analyzing statistical data and can be applied across various fields of knowledge, such as education, health, social, sciences, among others. According to Fonseca (2002):

Unlike qualitative Research, the results of quantitative Research can be measured numerically. Since the samples are generally large and considered representative of the population, the results are taken as if they portray profile of the entire target population of the research. (Fonseca, 2002, p. 20)

The previously mentioned author discusses a fundamental difference between qualitative and quantitative Research, highlighting how results are handled and interpreted in the quantitative approach. As stated, this approach allows results to be expressed in numbers, which facilitates statistical analysis.

According to Santos (2008, p. 26), “Mathematics provides modern science not only with the privileged instrument of analysis, but also with the logic of investigation, as well as the model for representing the very structure of matter.” Thus, it is possible to present the results found through numbers, tables, and graphs, as well as to establish relationships between the variables.

The research was conducted at the Municipal Department of Education and 15 elementary schools within the Municipal Network of a city in the southwest of Bahia, where interaction with the situations, environment, and the object of study was more prolonged and frequent.

The population consisted of 112 teachers who were invited, of whom 84 fully completed the data collection instrument. The research took place between September and October 2023, lasting approximately six weeks—a period that included the dissemination of the invitation, participant consent, and completion of the electronic questionnaire. Access to the teachers was obtained through authorization from the Municipal Department of Education and by sending the instrument link via *WhatsApp*.

As an inclusion criterion, we used the prerogative that the teacher should be actively working and teaching at the elementary level. Teacher participation was based on their voluntary involvement in the research. The exclusion criteria were teachers who were assigned to other duties and/or on any type of leave.

Regarding research instruments, the teachers were given a questionnaire validated by Moreira, Mussi, and Cardoso (2022). We present here the sociodemographic data obtained through this questionnaire. For quality of life, the World Health Organization Quality of Life Instrument Bref (WHOQOL-Bref) questionnaire was used.

The WHOQOL-Bref is a research instrument developed by the World Health Organization (WHO) with the purpose of assessing quality of life. It is recommended for use with adults and consists of 26 items that inquire about how the respondent perceives quality of life. According to Ferentz (2017), the WHOQOL-Bref was abbreviated from the original method and reduced to 26 questions. This new format is based on dividing the general quality of life questions (numbers one and two) and the remaining items into four domains: physical, psychological, social relationships, and environment.

Inviting teachers to participate in the research, contact was made with the school administration and coordination. It was agreed that a meeting would be held according to each school's possibilities. Thus, some schools suggested an in-person meeting, others opted for the online platform *Google Meet*, and in some cases, the coordinators volunteered to share the information and invite teachers themselves. Therefore, the awareness-raising process was carried out as suggested by the schools during August 2023.

After the entire awareness-raising process, a link was sent containing the Informed Consent Form and the questionnaires. Through this link, teachers could indicate their agreement or refusal to participate in the research. Thus, after consenting to participate, the teacher was directed to the questionnaire, which aimed to collect sociodemographic data, as well as information on professional characteristics, recognition, career, compensation, working conditions, and health. The same link also included the quality of life questionnaire (*World Health Organization Quality of Life Instrument Bref – WHOQOL-Bref*). The Informed Consent Form and the research questionnaires were transferred to Google Forms during August, and the link was made available to teachers via WhatsApp in September 2023, remaining accessible until October 2023.

The quantitative data were organized in *Microsoft Excel* and analyzed using *SPSS 20.0* software, employing descriptive statistics (means, standard deviations, and proportions) and the Pearson Chi-square test (Monte Carlo), with a significance level set at 5% ($p \leq 0.05$). The qualitative data from the interviews were processed using *IRAMUTEQ (Interface de R pour les Analyses Multidimensionnelles de Textes et de Questionnaires)*, which allows for the analysis of word frequency and co-occurrence. This software offers a wide range of tools for analyzing qualitative data based on textual statistics or lexicometry, and although the researcher remains the main driver of the research, their role is enhanced by *IRAMUTEQ*, which enables the interpretation of results already processed with scientific rigor (Castro Neta; Cardoso, 2021).

For comparison purposes, the variable “quality of life” was categorized into two groups—high and low—defined based on the median of the scores obtained in the questionnaires.

The theoretical and documentary references supporting the analysis were selected from recognized and publicly accessible sources, prioritizing indexed articles and institutional reports from national and international bodies (Fiocruz, OECD, INEP, and WHO), ensuring the traceability, reliability, and timeliness of the evidence used.

The project was approved by the Research Ethics Committee (COEP) of the State University of Bahia (UNEB), under the opinion number CAE 5.306.315, in compliance with all ethical guidelines established by Resolution No. 466/2012 of the National Health Council. All participants signed the Informed Consent Form (ICF) before the start of data collection.

Analysis and results

- Profile and general perception of quality of life

The analysis is based on the understanding that teachers' quality of life is not limited to the absence of illness, but rather reflects the degree of recognition, autonomy, and intellectual fulfillment that educators experience in their work environment.

The sample consisted of 84 teachers from the municipal education network, the majority of whom were female (82%), with an average age of 45 years and an average career length of 17 years. The predominance of women confirms the historical trend of the feminization of teaching, a phenomenon that links the act of teaching to the extension of caregiving and maternal roles. Both classic and recent studies on the subject indicate that this symbolic construction has established an image of teaching as a vocation rather than as an intellectual profession (Teixeira, 1998; Teixeira, 2022; Gatti, 2020; INEP, 2021).

The data in Table 1 presents the characteristics of the study sample. The chi-square test demonstrated an association between biological sex and the quality of life (QoL) of the research participants ($\chi^2(1) = 3.977$; $p = 0.046$). It is possible to understand that there was a connection between being a woman and working in teaching with quality of life, since, according to the chi-square test, the association between biological sex and the quality of life of the women participating in this study was negative. Of the 69 female participants, 38 reported having a low quality of life, according to the average, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1 – Sociodemographic profile of Elementary Teachers at the city of Pindaí – Bahia

	QoL low	QoL high	Total
Age (years)	46,45±9,58	44,05±9,31	45,25±9,47
Biological sex			
Feminine	38 (48,23%)	31 (36,9%)	69
Masculine	4 (4,76%)	11 (13,09%)	15
Marital status			
Married	34 (45,23%)	34 (40,5%)	68
Single	8 (9,5%)	8 (9,5%)	16
Graduation			
Human Sciences	37 (44%)	36 (42,9%)	73
Nature Sciences	1 (1,2%)	1 (1,2%)	2
Language	4 (4,8%)	2 (2,4%)	6
Human Sciences and Language	0	1 (1,2%)	1
Mathematics	0	2 (2,2%)	2

Employment status

Permanent employee	29 (34,5 %)	26 (31%)	55
Temporary contract	13 (15,5%)	16 (19%)	29

Source: Data from the research (2023).

About 81% of teachers are married. There was no association between the QoL and the marital status and the number of children ($p > 0,05$). Human Sciences (86,9%) was the most prevalent graduation. According to the obtained results, about 84 participants (65,50%) are permanent.

We observe in Table 1 that the average of the participants in the questionnaires, as presents in the Table, is 45.25. The youngest participant is 24 years old, and the oldest is 60 years old. According to the Census (Brazil, 2022), the average age of teachers working in Elementary Education in Brazil is between 40 and 49 years (Brazil, 2023). In a study conducted in a municipality in southwestern Bahia with high school teachers, the predominant age group among those surveyed was 30 to 39 years, representing 59% of the population (Seixas; Teixeira; Cardoso, 2025). There was no association between quality of life (QoL) and age ($p > 0,05$). However, the physical domain showed a weak association with the age of the participants ($r = -0.236$; $p = 0.031$).

According to research data and the School Census (2022), Brazilian Basic Education is mostly taught by women. “Of the teaching staff, composed of 2.3. billion professionals, 1.8 million (79.2%) are female teachers” (Inep, 2023, n.p.). “In Elementary Education from 1st to 9th grade, the percentage of women is 77.5% of the 1.4 million teachers” (Inep, 2023, n.p.).

Hypólito (2020, p. 68) says that the “phenomenon of feminization of teaching followed up the development of industrialization and urbanization accordingly to the capitalist social formation”. Women shows themselves in the world of work and, therefore, it is perceptive that the feminine public is a majority in the teaching field.

When we analyze the influence of the biological sex with the QoL, it was possible to verify that most women associate with low QoL. According to Santos and Gonçalves (2022), it is very common to constat that women need to adjust their careers with other daily functions, especially the care of the house, the children and other family members.

According to Lima *et al* (2021), in the work “The feminization of teaching and the construction of maternity”, in a general way, still these days, most of the challenges found by work women lays in the conciliation of the activities of work and the care of

the house, especially for those who have children. Most of the time, women blame themselves for not achieve the several activities that they need to do, most of it because of the imposition of the sexist society that believes that the work at home belongs to the women alone.

Teixeira (1998) names this process as deintellectualization of teaching. He says that teaching has been reduced to administrative, affection or management of conflict practices. This focus keeps the teacher away from the critical and reflexive dimension. He says that there is na overlay of non-pedagogical tasks – bureaucratic meetings, filling reports, social caring activities. All these activities fragilizes the professional identity of the teacher and contribute to the exhaustion. In small towns, like the town analyzed in this text, where the number of teachers is reduced and the comunitary demands lay down in the school, these effects become even more visible.

64% of the participants had affective connections and 36% act in temporary contracts. This indicates the instability in work relations and the decision dependency of the local administrative-political. This precariousness, debated by Campos, Vêras and Araújo (2020), creates insecurity and reduces the autonomy of the teacher, factors that resonates in the perception of quality of life and in the institutional belonging.

The application of the Questionnaire of Teacher Quality of Life (Q – TQL) showed that 53,6% of teachers had the perception of low quality of life, while 46,4% have a high quality of life, considering it as the median of the scores. It was observed the significative statistic difference between sex ($p = 0,046$), with major concentration in the low quality of life between women. This result reinforces the related evidence for national studies (Campos; Vêras; Araújo, 2020; Oliveira; Santos; Dias, 2017) and internationals (OCDE, 2023), that associates the excess of emotional and domestics tasks to the exhaustion and to the mental suffering of Elementary School teachers.

Although men have shown bigger scores in quality of life, it cannot infer causality. The difference can reflect asymmetry in the social expectations and in the work and familiar conditions, frequently without the same symbolic recognition. This finding dialogue with Fiocruz (2022) and with Teixeira's studies (1998; 2022), since they reveal that the teacher suffering is connect not only to the hours of word, but also to the loss of intellectual and political way of teacher work.

This result shows the necessity to understand the well-being of the teacher as a multidimensional and historical phenomenon, articulating material, symbolical and institutional dimensions. In this view, Cardoso Júnior et al (2025) identify a positive moderate to strong correlation ($r=0,56$) between quality of life and financial sufficiency when they researched teachers in Graduate levels. In this context, professional valorization demands much more than salary policies. It requires the recognition of teaching as a work of thinking, creation and cultural mediation.

- Analysis of physical, psychological, social and ambiental fields

In the results by domains of WHOQOL-Bref, the lowest average scores concentrate in the psychological and physical dimensions. This indicates the prevalence of exhaustion, muscular pain, sleep disturbances and emotional exhaustion among teachers. These symptoms dialogue with the concept of symbolic work suffering (Oliveira; Santos & Dias, 2017) and reflect a scenario of teacher malaise already described by Friocruz (2022) and by OCDE(2023).

Through the analysis realized with the teacher's answers, it was observed that the QoL was normally distributed ($W(84)= 0,994$; $p=0,912$). The QoL and its domains are shown in Table 2.

Table 2 – Domains of quality of life of teachers of Elementary School of Pindaí – BA (WHOQOL-bref)

	N	Minimum	Maximun	Average	Standard deviation
Physical Domain	84	28,6	96,4	65,01	13,54
Psychological Domain	84	37,5	100	69,69	11,83
Social Domain	84	16,7	100	71,03	16,08
Ambiental Domain	84	31,3	100	56,06	11,66
QoL	84	36,8	99,1	65,44	10,90

Source: Research Data SPSS (2023).

Table 2 refers to domains of quality of life. In this way, the physical domain, with lower average than the overall average of the instrument, expresses the direct impact of the overload and of the precarious conditions of the scholar infrastructure – overcrowded rooms, absence of pedagogical equipment and accumulation of classes. For Campos, Vêras and Araújo (2020), the physical deterioration of teachers can not be dissociated from management forms that intensifies the rhythm of work and naturalized the illness as a part of scholar routine.

At the psychological domain, the equally low indexes suggest a persistent anxiety, feeling of helplessness and low self-realization frame. These findings converge with Teixeira (2022) analysis, in which the teaching, especially in the municipal public schools, are dealing with a process of deintellectualization, in which the critical and reflexive dimension is replaced by bureaucratic tasks and institutional control. Such displacement directly affects the teacher's self-esteem, because the teacher does not recognize himself as an author of knowledge and becomes to see him or herself as a norm executor.

The social relation domain presented intermediaries scores. Although teachers related good coexistence among colleagues and mutual support in crise moments, isolation and desvalorization reports emerged by the management instances and from community. These data are like the finding of Gariglio (2010), that identifies in public schools a micropolitical mark for hierarchical relations and low symbolical recognition to the teacher intellectual work.

The ambiental domain was the most heterogeneous, with scores varying according to the bond and the local of work. Teachers with temporary contracts related to financial insecurity and low satisfaction with transportation, security and leisure, which reinforces the idea that the quality of teacher life strongly depends on structural conditions of the territory. The OCDE (2023) highlights that public policies of appreciation - such as stability and paid time for training – are fundamentals for teacher well-being.

Overall, the integrated analysis of the four domains shows that the quality of life of teachers does not limit to the individual sphere, but it reflects a work structure that combines precariousness and intensification and loss of intellectual meaning. As Teixeira (1998;2022) says, teaching became a tensioned field between the humanist ideal of education and the administrative logic of public policies, producing a paradox between vocation and exhaustion.

This results, therefore, points to the urgency of politics thar articulates mental health, professional autonomy and intellectual recognition, overcoming the compensatory model centered only in training or in productivity bonus.

- Interpretative synthesis and implications

The synthesis of the results reinforces that the quality of teacher's life is a structural phenomenon, not individual. The reported challenges by the participants – fatigue, anxiety, demotivation and loss of recognition – cannot be explained solely by personal factors, but by organizational and symbolical conditions that degrade the meaning of educational work.

This frame reveals what Teixeira (1998) conceptualized as “process of deintellectualization of teacher work”: the erosion of the critical and creational dimension of the teacher, exchanged by bureaucratic demanding and tasks of social care that extrapolates the pedagogical nature of the work. When the work of the teacher is reduced to the execution of protocols and reports, the school distances itself from its formative function and the teacher from his or her intellectual identity.

The feminization of teaching, in this context, acquires new contours. More than a demographic characteristic, it is about a political condition of symbolic subordination, that associates the educational work to patient, empathy and obedience – virtues historically attributed to woman and appreciated in detriment to the autonomy and critical thinking. Teixeira (1998) and Gatti (2020) point that this logic perpetuates inequalities and naturalize the emotional and moral overload imposed to the women who are teachers.

On the other hand, evidence also shows resistance potential: emotional bonds, mutual support, feeling of belongingness to the school and desire to continue in the teaching field. This element indicates that, despite the precariousness, the teacher's work is still sustained about this ethic and affectionate ties of collective commitments.

So, the article proposes to understand the quality of life of teachers as a field of dispute between the forces of emptying and “rehumanizing” emotional work. By situating the suffering of teachers in a structural and historical perspective, the need for public policies is reaffirmed and they need to surpass the welfare and advance to institutional models of care, autonomy and intellectual authorship.

As OCDE (2023) says, the educational systems that preserve the well-being and the autonomy of teachers also are the ones who reaches the best indicators of learning and innovation. In this sense, taking care of teachers' lives is not a charity gesture, but an ethical and political imperative.

Final considerations

Conducting Research on the quality of teaching life is quite challenging, given the multiple concepts that encompass the term quality of life. Thus, discussing this topic allowed us to reflect on teacher's daily involvement in their practice, allowing us to infer the particularities that permeate their profession and the various duties and responsibilities imposed on them, whether within the sphere in which they are employed or at the school where they teach.

The research showed that the quality of teaching life is closely linked to the objective and symbolic conditions of work, reflecting the tensions between the educational project and the current management model. In this sense, the analysis is based on the understanding that the quality of teaching life is not limited to the absence of illness, but reflects the degree of recognition, autonomy, and intellectual fulfillment of teachers in their work context. Empirical data revealed persistent physical exhaustion, psychological distress, and professional devaluation, especially among women, who make up most municipal teachers.

This reality confirms the structural nature of the feminization of teaching, historically associated with the naturalization of care and the deintellectualization of the profession – when the work of teaching is treated as an extension of moral and affective tasks, and not as a practice of thought and creation.

The physical domain was associated with poor quality of life. In this context, several factors were observed, such as energy, sleep and rest. Teachers complained about not receiving support with activities that could provide a better quality of life.

More than a descriptive category, quality of life here means a condition of possibility for the exercise of thought and sensitivity, a way of rehumanizing the profession in the face of precariousness and productivism.

The results also highlight the urgent need for public policies that recognize teaching as an intellectual activity, guaranteeing pedagogical autonomy, stability, paid study time, and institutional mental health care. These measures are not merely administrative: they constitute policies aimed at valuing teachers, improving their quality of life, and providing support to address issues such as stress and mental health, ensuring a healthier and more sustainable environment.

Finally, it is recognized that this study, although limited to a municipality in southwestern Bahia, offers a representative portrait of the contemporary conditions of public education in Brazil.

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